

E³UDRES²
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ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS + EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

Cooperating for **excellence**
and impact in **research**
and **innovation**

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Cooperating for excellence and impact in research and innovation

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators (entrepreneurs-researchers-educators-innovators) project brings together the six founding partners of this European consortium under construction since 2020 and **will be on the ground until 2025 with the mission of surveying the conditions of research work on the extensive E³UDRES² campus** - from Portugal to Latvia, passing through Hungary, Romania, Austria and Belgium.

E³UDRES² ENT-R-E-NOVATORS INCLUDES, INTERACTS AND COLLABORATES WITH A DIVERSE VARIETY OF SMART AND AMBITIOUS PEOPLE (...)

The project, that started in October 2022, is funded by the European Commission, through the Horizon Europe programme, within the framework of its pillar on scientific excellence (call HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05), which aims to strengthen the Research and Innovation capacity of higher education institutions, countries and their ecosystems.

In line with its vision, mission, core values, culture and principles, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project aims to co-create a more specific joint Research and Innovation Strategy and a common agenda to accelerate the transformation into a European multi-institutional Research and Innovation Hub for Smart and Sustainable Regions.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators include, interact and collaborate with a diverse variety of smart and ambitious people, academic

institutions, regional authorities, companies, European R&I networks and regional innovation ecosystems. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators is committed to scientific excellence and research integrity within its cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral key Research and Innovation (R&I) networks and promotes (future) R&I competencies, skills, resources, methods, training, services and management for collaborative research and open innovation for smart and sustainable regions.

Over 36 months of project work, E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators proposes to carry out a diagnosis of the existing capacity at the partner institutions in terms of Research and Innovation, focusing on fundamental areas such as infrastructure, equipment and human resources, activities, RD&I lines, groups and networks, as well as Open Science policies and practices and engagement with society.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project objectives

- **Objective 1:** Co-create a common strategy and agenda that unlocks our potential for excellence in Research and Innovation, to accelerate the transformation into a multi-institutional European Research and Innovation Centre for Smart and Sustainable Regions;

- **Objective 2:** Develop best practices and a strategy for pooling Research infrastructures, expertise, data and resources and for collaborating with/getting access to other strategic research infrastructures;

- **Objective 3:** Develop structured support programmes aimed at empowering our scientific communities to fully embrace Open Science (OS), Open Innovation (OI), Open Education (OE), Engaged Science and Engaged Education;

- **Objective 4:** Work to achieve a level playing field in terms of institutional strategies and policies for Human Resources for Research, from which we will be able to address bigger challenges, such as brain mobility, new career assessments and joint recruitment strategies;

- **Objective 5:** Develop a structured and integrated framework to seamlessly link all our R&I ecosystems and the E³UDRES² alliance's knowledge triangle of education, Research and Innovation;

- **Objective 6:** Along our pathway to build a common R&I agenda, be connected and dialogue with peer Alliances and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), HEI associations and advocacy groups, and policy-makers with a view to contribute with evidence based results to the co-creation of future EEA/ERA (European Education Area/European Research Area) work programmes and to inform better policies.

(...) THE E³UDRES² ALLIANCE'S KNOWLEDGE TRIANGLE OF EDUCATION, RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

The project team is divided into **6 work packages (WP)** with specific work focuses

- **WP1 | Leader:** Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal (IPS), Portugal

The Project Coordinator's primary responsibilities are to oversee the implementation of all WPs and ensure that all terms and conditions set out in the EC Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement are met.

- **WP2 | Leader:** Fachhochschule St Pölten GMBH (STPUAS), Austria

This WP will map and strengthen synergies and critical mass around common Research and Innovation priorities. One of its main outcomes is setting up a multi-institutional R&I agenda that incorporates E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators human-centered and challenge-based approach with a special focus on the further development of European Smart and Sustainable Regions.

- **WP3 | Leader:** Magyar Agrár- és Élettudományi Egyetem (MATE), Hungary

This WP ensures the efficient, sustainable and agile implementation of RD&I collaboration and resource sharing using the simple tools of classical business strategy planning. Accordingly, the strategic planning process will identify the strengths and weaknesses of the collaborating organisations' RD&I infrastructure and identify opportunities and threats in the regulatory and technological environment.

- **WP4 | Leader:** Universitatea Politehnica Timișoara (UPT), Romania

Assess the current status of the six partner institutions in terms of open practices: what are our strengths, weaknesses (gaps) and overall adequacy of Open Science/Open Innovation/Open Education (OS/OI/OE) tools, resources and training. Based on that, this WP team will evaluate and validate options and develop a common strategy for OS/OI/OE.

- **WP5 | Leader:** UC Limburg (UCLL), Belgium

Collect and co-create engagement models for researchers and citizens to engage, evaluate and inspire their perception and expectations for citizen science projects.

- **WP6 | Leader:** Vidzemes Augstskola (ViA), Latvia

Researchers are our greatest asset for driving the innovation needed to create smart and sustainable regions. One of the goals of this WP is to develop a Human Resources strategy able to empower E³UDRES² researchers. The second one is to connect them with the regions and the key stakeholders who will facilitate innovation uptake, through the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystems.

E³UDRES² is an alliance for the future European education

(...) CAPABLE OF MAKING THEM ACTIVE AGENTS THAT CONTRIBUTE TO THE **DEVELOPMENT OF SMART AND SUSTAINABLE REGIONS.**

E³UDRES² is an alliance that forms part of a new concept of European Higher Education that is still in the implementation phase. The aim of the Future Universities' initiative is to create a disruption in European education, supporting the transition to what will be the universities of the future, in the 2030 horizon. Cooperating closely with the community and the region, this model uses new student-focused teaching approaches and methodologies, capable of making them active agents that contribute to the development of smart and sustainable regions.

1. Beneficiary of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators
2. Joining E³UDRES² from Autumn 2023

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